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Allometric Shape Change in the Chicken Humerus and Femur

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ABSTRACT

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This study compared the relative strength of size-related shape change (allometry) in the chicken humerus and femur using three-dimensional geometric morphometrics. The dataset comprised 15 unilateral humeri and 15 unilateral femora. Bones were boiled to remove soft tissues, cleaned with hydrogen peroxide, and digitized with an EinScan SP V2 desktop 3D scanner. Landmark placement was performed automatically in 3D Slicer using the ALPACA module, with 18 landmarks for the humerus and 20 for the femur. The relationship between Procrustes shape coordinates and log-transformed centroid size was tested separately for each element with procD.lm and a residual randomization permutation procedure (RRPP; 10,000 permutations). The humerus model contained 54 dependent shape variables and the femur model 60; in both analyses, the effective data-space dimension was 14. Size explained 6.04% of total shape variation in the humerus and 4.95% in the femur, leaving 93.96% and 95.05% of variation unexplained by size, respectively. The descriptive allometric signal was thus approximately 1.09 percentage points, or about 22% relatively, higher in the humerus. However, neither model was statistically significant (humerus: $F = 0.8364$, $Z = 0.0386$, $p = 0.4846$; femur: $F = 0.6772$, $Z = -0.2769$, $p = 0.6000$). These findings indicate a slightly stronger but still weak allometric tendency in the humerus and suggest that a larger and biologically better controlled sample is required to demonstrate any robust element-specific difference. This study specifically evaluates static (intraspecific) allometry within a limited size range.

I. INTRODUCTION

Allometry is defined as the systematic change of shape with size and is a central concept in developmental biology, functional anatomy, and evolutionary morphology (Klingenberg, 2016; Mitteroecker, Gunz, Windhager, & Schaefer, 2013). Geometric morphometrics has become one of the standard approaches for evaluating allometric patterns because it preserves shape information through landmark coordinates and allows size-shape covariation to be examined within a multivariate regression framework (Adams & Otárola-Castillo, 2013; Klingenberg, 2022).

In the avian skeleton, the humerus and femur are two long bones operating under distinct functional loading regimes. The humerus is the main element transmitting forces between the pectoral girdle and the wing; forces generated by the major flight muscles and aerodynamic loads are transferred to this bone, and the humeral shaft is known to experience marked torsional and bending stresses (Biewener & Dial, 1995; Habib & Ruff, 2008). By contrast, the femur is more closely associated with postural support, load transfer, and locomotor muscle function in the hindlimb, and femoral shape therefore has to be interpreted within a different mechanical and functional context (Wei & Zhang, 2019; Bishop et al., 2021).

Recent advances in three-dimensional digitization and automated landmarking have greatly improved the repeatable and high-resolution quantification of skeletal morphology. In particular, the 3D Slicer and SlicerMorph ecosystem has made ALPACA an accessible tool for rapid landmark transfer between surface models, with the aim of reducing observer-

driven variability (Fedorov et al., 2012; Rolfe et al., 2021; Porto, Rolfe, & Maga, 2021). At the same time, it has been reported that multi-template strategies can further improve automated landmark accuracy when within-sample variation is broader (Zhang, Porto, Rolfe, Kocatulum, & Maga, 2022).

Because the dataset represents within-species variation, the analyses are interpreted in the context of static/intraspecific allometry (Klingenberg, 2016). The specific research question was which bone shows the stronger allometric signal. The working hypothesis was that the different functional roles of forelimb and hindlimb elements may produce element-specific divergence in size-shape covariation.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Material preparation and samples

Chicken (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) skeletal material was used in this study. Bones were boiled to remove soft tissues and cleaned with hydrogen peroxide. Only unilateral bones were included in the analysis. The dataset consisted of 15 humeri and 15 femora.

This design reduced the independence problem that might arise from bilateral repetition, while also making it possible to evaluate the size-shape relationship within each element separately.

2.2. Three-dimensional scanning and landmarking

The cleaned bones were scanned with an EinScan SP V2 desktop 3D scanner and surface models were obtained. Landmark placement was performed automatically in 3D Slicer/SlicerMorph using the ALPACA module.

Fig. 1. Automated three-dimensional (3D) landmark configurations applied to the humerus (A) and femur (B). Two views are presented for each bone to illustrate spatial distribution. A total of 18 landmarks were used for the humerus and 20 landmarks for the femur. Landmarks were distributed across the proximal epiphysis, diaphysis (shaft), and distal epiphysis to ensure comprehensive representation of overall bone morphology and functionally relevant regions

Eighteen anatomical landmarks were defined for the humerus and 20 for the femur. These points were distributed across the proximal end, shaft, and distal end of each bone. Landmarks were selected to represent anatomically homologous regions across the proximal, shaft, and distal parts of each bone, ensuring consistent coverage of functional morphology. The landmark configurations used in the study are shown in Fig. 1.

2.3. Geometric morphometrics and statistical analysis

Landmark coordinates were imported into R and each bone was analyzed separately. Because the data files already contained Procrustes-aligned coordinates and centroid size information, statistical

evaluation was performed on those coordinates directly. The allometric relationship was defined as a multivariate regression of shape variables on log-transformed centroid size.

For each element, the statistical model was specified as $\text{shape} \sim \log(\text{centroid size})$ and tested with `procD.lm`. Significance was evaluated with the RRPP (Residual Randomization in a Permutation Procedure) approach using 10,000 permutations (Collyer & Adams, 2018). Because different numbers of landmarks were used for the humerus and femur, the analyses were conducted in separate shape spaces; therefore, absolute centroid size values and absolute sums of squares were not used for direct biological comparison between bones. For each bone, R^2 , F, Z, and p values were reported. In addition, model sums of squares, residual variance,

and effective data-space dimension were used for descriptive interpretation. All results were evaluated at $\alpha = 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

Fifteen specimens were included in the analyses for each bone. The humerus model contained 54 dependent shape variables and the femur model 60; however, owing to sample size, the effective data-space dimension was 14 in both analyses. This indicates that statistical inference was constrained more strongly by the number of specimens than by the nominal number of coordinate variables.

According to the permutation-based Procrustes regression results, the explanatory sums of squares for the \log_size term were 0.012757 in the humerus and 0.003264 in the femur. Residual sums of squares were 0.198290 for the humerus and 0.062655 for the femur. Total Procrustes sums of squares were 0.211048 and 0.065919, respectively; however, this absolute difference should not be interpreted as evidence of greater overall morphological variance in one element, because it is influenced by the different landmark counts and distinct shape spaces. Size explained 6.04% of total shape variation in the humerus ($R^2 = 0.0604$) and 4.95% in the femur

($R^2=0.0495$). Conversely, residual variance remained high, at 93.96% in the humerus and 95.05% in the femur. The proportion of explained variance was therefore approximately 1.09 percentage points, or about 22% relatively, higher in the humerus.

For the humerus, the allometric model yielded $F = 0.8364$, $Z = 0.0386$, and $p = 0.4846$; for the femur, the corresponding values were $F = 0.6772$, $Z = -0.2769$, and $p = 0.6000$. In both models, F values remained below 1 and Z statistics were close to zero, indicating that the observed size effect did not depart strongly from the permutation-based null expectation (Table 1). Thus, although the humerus displayed a slightly stronger descriptive allometric tendency than the femur, the size-shape relationship was not statistically significant in either bone.

In other words, the dominant portion of shape variation in this sample appears to be independent of size. Rather than demonstrating that the humerus is clearly more allometric than the femur, the results suggest that any possible difference between the elements could not be established reliably with the present sample. All numerical values were reported using consistent decimal formatting throughout the analysis.

Table 1. Summary results of the Procrustes allometry models for the humerus and femur.

Bone	n	Landmarks	Shape vars.	Data space	R ²	Residual %	F	Z	p
Femur	15	20	60	14	0.0495	95.05	0.6772	-0.2769	0.6000
Humerus	15	18	54	14	0.0604	93.96	0.8364	0.0386	0.4846

Note. Shape vars. = number of Procrustes coordinate variables; residual % = proportion of variance not explained by size.

4. DISCUSSION

The main finding of this study is that the allometric signal is weak in both the chicken humerus and femur and does not reach statistical significance. In a within-species dataset with a presumably limited size range, the relationship tested here reflects static/intraspecific allometry rather than ontogenetic allometry, and it is therefore not surprising that size explains only a modest fraction of total shape variance (Klingenberg, 2016, 2022). In this sense, R^2 values of roughly 5-6% point to a weak but plausible tendency rather than to a strong allometric structure.

The slightly higher R^2 observed in the humerus is biologically plausible from a functional anatomical perspective. The humerus is the key forelimb bone in birds and operates under the combined effects of major flight muscles and aerodynamic loads; experimental work has shown pronounced torsional and bending regimes in the humeral shaft during flight (Biewener & Dial, 1995). Broader comparative studies have also shown that humeral morphology is closely associated with locomotor regime and mode of wing use (Habib & Ruff, 2008; Serrano et al., 2020). It is therefore theoretically reasonable to expect more flexible size-related reorganization in the humerus than in the femur, whether in muscle attachment regions, proximal morphology, or shaft organization.

By contrast, the lower proportion of explained variance in the femur may suggest that hindlimb elements behave more conservatively in shape because of their roles in postural support and terrestrial locomotion. Studies of avian hindlimbs indicate strong functional integration among femoral mechanics, joint kinematics, and muscle operating ranges (Wei & Zhang, 2019; Bishop et al., 2021).

However, the critical point is that the apparent advantage of the humerus remains descriptive only. The high p values and near-zero Z statistics clearly show that a strong element-specific divergence cannot yet be demonstrated from this dataset.

The fact that size-unexplained variance remained very high - 93.96% in the humerus and 95.05% in the femur - suggests that much of the observed shape variation is linked to biological and environmental variables other than size. Age, sex, growth stage, mechanical use, husbandry conditions, and breed history may all be relevant in this context. Variation related to domestication and breed formation has also been documented in the chicken skeleton (Herrera-Castillo et al., 2022). Consequently, a considerable part of the among-individual variation may have been absorbed into the residual component because these factors were not modelled explicitly.

Sample size is one of the clearest limitations of the study. The limited sample size likely reduced statistical power and contributed to the inability to detect statistically significant allometric relationships. With only 15 specimens per element, the analysis of high-dimensional shape data represented by 54 and 60 coordinate variables was necessarily constrained; accordingly, the RRPP output limited the effective data space to 14 dimensions in both models. The geometric morphometric literature shows that small samples can inflate sampling error, especially when estimating mean shape, allometric directions, and pattern contrasts (Cardini & Elton, 2007). The lack of significance found here should therefore be interpreted less as proof of an absence of allometry and more as evidence that any allometric pattern could not be detected strongly with the current sample.

One of the strengths of the study is the combination of 3D surface scanning and automated landmarking. The 3D Slicer/SlicerMorph ecosystem and ALPACA pipeline offer important advantages for accelerating data collection and reducing researcher-dependent landmark placement variation (Fedorov et al., 2012; Rolfe et al., 2021; Porto et al., 2021). At the same time, the lack of validation of the automated landmarks against manual landmarking, together with the potential template bias inherent to a single-template approach, remains a methodological limitation. When within-sample morphological diversity is broader, the multi-template MALPACA approach has been reported to provide more robust results (Zhang et al., 2022), and it would therefore be a useful direction for future work. Despite these limitations, the use of automated landmarking provides a reproducible and efficient framework for high-resolution morphological analysis.

In addition, the use of different landmark counts and different anatomical configurations for the humerus and femur means that the two bones cannot be compared directly within a single common shape space. Accordingly, the present evaluation should be understood as a descriptive comparison of the relative strength of two independent regression models rather than as a direct cross-element test in a homologous space. Future studies incorporating larger samples, age/sex/breed information, manual-versus-automatic landmark validation, and regression score visualization with deformation maps would be better positioned to test whether a biologically meaningful allometric divergence truly exists between the two elements.

5. CONCLUSION

In the present dataset, size explained 6.04% of shape variation in the humerus and 4.95% in the femur. Although the descriptive allometric signal in the humerus appeared approximately 22% higher than in the femur, both models were statistically non-significant and more than 93% of the variance remained independent of size. Accordingly, this study does not yet demonstrate a strong and distinct element-specific allometric divergence between the chicken humerus and femur. Nevertheless, it provides a comparative baseline based on 3D geometric morphometrics and automated landmarking, and it offers a solid starting point for future work using larger, biologically better characterized, and methodologically validated samples. These findings should be interpreted cautiously due to the limited sample size and lack of statistical significance.

Ethical Approval

The materials used in this study were obtained from animals slaughtered for food production, and no animals were sacrificed specifically for research purposes. Therefore, ethical approval was not required.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

The study was conceptualized, designed, supervised, and conducted collaboratively by Hadji Chiuta Salimu and Muhammed Zahid Atli. Both authors contributed to resource provision, material supply, data collection

and processing, analysis and interpretation, manuscript writing, and critical review.

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